

The Stereochemistry of Trivalent Nitrogen Compounds.
Part I. The Attempted Resolution of Some
Substituted Derivatives of Aniline.

BY E. V. MENON AND D. H. PEACOCK.

Mills and Elliott (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1298) resolved benzenesulphonyl 8-nitro-1-naphthylglycine but ascribed the dissymmetry to the restriction of the free rotation of the nitrogen atom and not to the absence of a planar configuration for this atom. With the exception of this compound and some others of a similar type (Mills and Breckenridge, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 431) no substance appears to be known in which the optical activity arises from a nitrogen atom not doubly linked to carbon or forming part of a ring. In view of the close formal resemblance between the electronic configurations of trivalent nitrogen compounds of type I and the sulphinic esters (II)

and sulphoxides (III) it appeared desirable to attempt the resolution of the following compounds :—

The compound (IV) readily gave a crystalline brucine salt from which, after repeated crystallisations, only an inactive sodium salt was

obtained ; no other crystalline salt could be obtained with the alkaloids tried (*cf.* Peacock, *Dissertation*, London University, 1927 ; Meisenheimer, *Ber.*, 1924, **56**, 1744 ; Jones and Millington, *Proc. Camb. Phil. Soc.*, 1904, **12**, vi, 489). The compounds (V) and (VI) readily gave crystalline tartrates but these salts could not be resolved. The compound (VI, *m*) was converted into the methiodide in the hope that the strongly basic quaternary salt would readily give a crystalline camphorsulphonate or bromcamphorsulphonate but both these salts failed to crystallise. The compound (V) was condensed with α -methyl-*p*-phenoxybutyryl chloride and gave (VII)

(VII)

but this substance appeared homogeneous (*cf.* Kipping and Salway, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 438). The compound VI (*meta* and *para*) behaved similarly. None of the substances examined showed signs of dissymmetry.

In the course of this work it was observed that the sodium salt of *p*-toluenesulphonyl-*p*-nitroaniline reacted with benzyl chloride much less readily than did the corresponding derivatives of *m*-nitraniline. This behaviour resembles that of *m*- and *p*-nitranilines with benzyl chloride (Peacock, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **127**, 2177) and is being further examined.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Brucine salt of ethylbenzylaniline sulphonic acid (IV).—Ethylbenzylaniline was sulphonated with 20% oleum at 80°. The crystalline acid and brucine in molecular proportions were dissolved in hot alcohol and the solution allowed to cool, when the brucine salt separated in long needles, *m. p.* 164-5°, sparingly soluble in cold alcohol and less soluble in the other common organic solvents. (Found : S, 4'75, 4'48, 4'65. $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{43}\text{O}_7\text{N}_3\text{S}$ requires, S, 4'67 per cent). This compound was crystallised 5 times from alcohol and then converted to the sodium salt which was found inactive.

p-Toluenesulphonylbenzyl-*m*-nitroaniline.—*p*-Toluenesulphonyl-*m*-nitroaniline was prepared by a slight modification of the method described by Morgan and Micklethwait (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, **89**,

1292). *m*-Nitraniline (69 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (47.6 g.) and toluene (500 c. c.) were heated on a water-bath under reflux condenser until the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased (20 hours). Toluene (100 c. c.) was then added and the *m*-nitraniline extracted by concentrated hydrochloric acid. The sulphonyl derivative was then extracted by caustic soda, acidified with hydrochloric acid and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 136.7°, yield 87%. This substance (58.4 g. with caustic soda (8 g.) was dissolved in warm alcohol (300 c.c.) and benzyl chloride (25.3 g.) added. The mixture was boiled under reflux on a water-bath until neutral (4 hours). The solvent was distilled off, the residue extracted with dilute caustic soda and the pale yellow product (58 g.) crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 118°. (Found: N, 7.4; S, 8.42. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 7.33; S, 8.37 per cent).

p-Toluenesulphonyl-benzyl-*m*-phenylenediamine (VI, meta)—The nitro compound (50 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (250 c. c.) and tin (50 g.) added. Hydrochloric acid (85 c.c.) was added, 5 c.c. at a time, and the mixture heated under reflux for 6 hours on a water-bath. The solvent was removed by distillation and the residue basified with sodium carbonate. The mixture of tin oxide and base was filtered and the base extracted with hot alcohol, when the base was obtained as colourless crystals, rapidly darkening on exposure to air, m. p. 127°, yield 40 g. (Found: N, 7.9; S, 8.86. $C_{20}H_{20}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 7.96; S, 9.09 per cent). The acid tartrate crystallised on cooling by adding tartaric acid (6.0 g.) to the base (14 g.) dissolved in warm alcohol (100 c. c.), m. p. 136°. It is very soluble in acetone and chloroform, sparingly soluble in cold alcohol and benzene. (Found: N, 5.77; S, 6.48. $C_{24}H_{28}O_8N_2S$ requires N, 5.57; S, 6.37 per cent). The salt was crystallised from alcohol, $[\alpha]_D^{28}$ (acetone, $p=5.024$ g.), 4.57°; whence $[M]_D^{28}=23.0^\circ$. After three crystallisations the solution ($p=5.0196$ g.) had $[\alpha]_D^{28}$, 4.67°; $[M]_D^{28}$, 23.5, and after twelve crystallisations $[\alpha]_D^{28}$, 4.57; $[M]_D^{28}$, 23.1° ($p=5.0224$ g.). The salt isolated from the mother liquors had $[\alpha]_D^{28}$, 4.57°; $[M]_D^{28}$, 23.1° ($p=5.0204$ g.). *p*-Toluidine hydrogen tartrate in acetone ($p=2.5672$ g.) had $[\alpha]_D^{28}$, 8.56°; $[M]_D^{28}$, 22.0°. No resolution seems, therefore, to have been effected.

p-Toluenesulphonyl-*m*-dimethylaminophenylbenzylamine.—The amine (7 g.) was mixed with water (100 c. c.), sodium carbonate (3.2 g.) and methyl iodide (6 g.) and heated under reflux on a water-bath for 3 hours. Caustic soda was added and the oily base solidified on cooling and finally crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 101°, yield 7 g. (Found: N, 7.53. $C_{22}H_{24}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 7.37 per cent).

The *methiodide* of the preceding compound was prepared in two ways: (a) The tertiary base (3.5 g.) was mixed with methyl iodide (2.0 g.) and left for some days. The excess of methyl iodide was removed by evaporation and the residue crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 111°. (b) The primary base (VI) (3.5 g.), methyl iodide (5 g.) and water (100 c. c.) were heated under reflux on a water-bath for 5 hours. The quaternary salt separated as an oil which solidified when cold and was finally crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 111-112°. (Found: I, 23.95. $C_{23}H_{27}O_2N_2IS$ requires I, 24.32 per cent). This iodide with silver bromcamphor sulphionate gave only a gummy product.

α-Methyl-γ-phenoxybutyryl derivative of (VI) (meta).—The amine (VI, meta) (3.5 g.) was dissolved in ether and *α*-methyl-*γ*-phenoxybutyryl chloride (2.3 g.) in ether (25 c. c.) added. The reaction was vigorous. The ether was distilled off and the amine hydrochloride removed by dilute hydrochloric acid. The amide was left as an oil which solidified after some days. It was crystallised 5 times from alcohol, each fraction melting at 117°; from the mother liquors the recovered substance melted at 116°, mixed m. p. 115-16°. (Found: N, 5.44. $C_{31}H_{32}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 5.29 per cent). The product seems homogeneous. *α*-methyl-*γ*-phenoxybutyric acid was prepared by the methylation of *β*-phenoxyethyl malonic ester prepared by the action of *β*-phenoxyethyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate on sodiomalonic ester (Peacock and Tha, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2303). The acid was converted into the acid chloride by thionyl chloride.

p-Toluenesulphonylbenzyl-p-nitroaniline.—*p*-Toluenesulphonyl-*p*-nitraniline (58.4 g., Morgan and Micklethwait, *loc. cit.*) was mixed with caustic soda (8.0 g.) in amyl alcohol (350 c. c.) and benzyl chloride (25.3 g.) added. The mixture was boiled for 12 hours under reflux in an oil-bath at 140-50° until neutral. In ethyl alcohol it was not neutral after a much longer period of heating. The amyl alcohol was distilled off from an oil-bath and the residue extracted with caustic soda solution. The product (54 g.) separated from alcohol in pale-yellow crystals, m.p. 128°. (Found: N, 7.5; S, 8.18. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 7.33; S, 8.37 per cent).

p-Toluenesulphonyl-benzyl-p-phenylenediamine (VI, para).—The nitro compound from the above (38.2 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (200 c. c.) and tin (40 g.) added. Concentrated hydrochloric acid (90 c. c.) was then added, 10 c. c. at a time, and reduction completed by heating on a water-bath for 8 hours. The product was worked up as before, yield of crude base 28 g. It separated from alcohol in

colourless crystals rapidly turning brown, m.p. 162°. (Found ; N, 8.02 ; S, 8.87. $C_{20}H_{20}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 7.96 ; S, 9.09 per cent). This base did not form a tartrate and the camphorsulphonate and bromcamphorsulphonate were non-crystalline.

α-methyl-γ-phenoxybutyryl derivative of (VI, para).—This was prepared from the base and the acid chloride in ether solution. The amide was crystallised 7 times from alcohol, m. p. of each fraction being 143°. The amide, recovered from the mother liquor, melted at 142°, mixed m. p. 142-3°. (Found : N, 5.22. $C_{31}H_{32}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 5.29 per cent).

p-Toluenesulphonyl-[m-nitrobenzyl]-aniline.—Sodium (2.3 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (100 c. c.) and *p*-toluenesulphoanilide (24.7 g.) added. The mixture was boiled under reflux on a water-bath for 10 minutes and the alcohol then distilled off. *m*-Nitrobenzyl chloride (17.2 g.) was added to the sodium compound, dried by two distillations with dry benzene, and the mixture heated in an oil-bath at 140-50° for 15 hours. The product was extracted with caustic soda solution and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 95°. (Found : N, 7.28 ; S, 8.28. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 7.33 ; S, 8.37 per cent).

p-Toluenesulphon-[m-aminobenzyl]-anilide (V).—The nitro compound from the above (30 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (200 c. c.) and tin (30 g.) added. Concentrated hydrochloric acid (55 c. c.) was then added gradually and reduction completed by heating for 5 hours under reflux on a water-bath. The product was worked up as before. The base (24 g.) was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 129°. (Found : N, 7.98 ; S, 8.81. $C_{20}H_{20}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 7.96 ; S, 9.09 per cent). The base V (14.0 g.) was dissolved in alcohol and tartaric acid (6.0 g.) added. The acid tartrate separated on cooling, m. p. 133°. (Found : N, 5.68 ; S, 6.21. $C_{24}H_{26}O_8N_2S$ requires N, 5.57 ; S, 6.37 per cent). After one crystallisation [α]_D²⁵ in acetone ($p=4.9992$ g.), 4.6° ; [M]_D²⁵, 23.0°, and after five crystallisations, [α]_D²⁵, 4.6° ; [M]_D²⁵, 23.0° ($p=5.0192$ g.). No resolution appears to have been effected. The camphor sulphonate and the bromocamphorsulphonate were not obtained crystalline.

α-methyl-γ-phenoxybutyryl derivative of (V) was prepared in the usual way in ether solution. It was fractionally crystallised from alcohol 5 times and each fraction melted at 111°. The product recovered from the mother liquors melted at 110° ; mixed m. p. 109-10°. (Found : N, 5.48. $C_{31}H_{32}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 5.29 per cent).

We have to thank the University of Rangoon for a grant in aid of this work which is being continued.